

Proactive Fault Detection in Wind Turbine Generators using SCADA Measurements

PREPRINT

A. Weissenfeld*, J. Vanerio*, A. Wachsenegger*, A. Graser*, A. Garos[†], S. Visvardi[‡], A. Ntafalias[§], P. Casas*

*AIT Austrian Institute of Technology, Vienna, Austria

{axel.weissenfeld, juan.vanerio, anita.graser, pedro.casas}@ait.ac.at

[†]R&D Department, Space Hellas S.A., Athens, Greece – agaros@space.gr

[‡]Motor Oil Renewable Energy, Athens, Greece – svisvardi@moreenergy.gr

[§]Motor Oil Hellas S.A., Athens, Greece – antafalias@moh.gr

Abstract—Predictive maintenance is essential in the wind energy sector due to the high costs and complexity of maintaining wind turbines operating in remote and harsh environments. This paper presents a proactive fault detection framework for wind turbine generators (WTGs) to enable early intervention, improve reliability, and minimize downtime associated with generator failures. The study is based on six years (2019–2024) of SCADA measurements from a wind farm with 10 WTGs in Greece, where generator failures account for a significant portion of major component breakdowns. The proposed approach leverages well-known shallow learning models, including the Quantile Regression Model (QRM), CatBoost, XGBoost, and LightGBM, to predict the normal operating range of generator bearing temperature using covariates derived from current and future SCADA signals. Anomalies are identified by analyzing the residuals between predicted and observed temperatures within a sliding window framework. The paper details critical preprocessing steps, such as filtering out data during and after failures and considering only effective wind speed and power production conditions. The experimental evaluation assesses the performance of different models in generator bearing temperature prediction and anomaly detection, emphasizing the impact of post-processing techniques on detection accuracy. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach in identifying early warning signs of generator failures but also indicate the current challenges due to low precision.

Index Terms—Predictive maintenance, anomaly detection, wind turbine generators, SCADA data, machine learning, residual analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Predictive maintenance (PrM) plays a crucial role in the wind energy sector [1] due to the unique challenges of this industry. These challenges include the remote locations of wind farms (WFs), the harsh operational conditions, and the large-scale deployment of turbines — making maintenance a costly and logistically complex task, which can account for 20-30% of the total power generation expenses [2]. Additionally, wind turbines inherently experience downtime

due to fluctuating wind conditions. By strategically aligning maintenance activities with these low-wind periods, operators can minimize unplanned downtime and optimize efficiency. This proactive approach not only reduces maintenance costs but also enhances the reliability of wind farms, facilitating their integration into the national energy grid.

To ensure reliable electricity production from wind turbine generators (WTGs), timely failure prediction of critical components, such as the generator, is essential. A survey [3] on wind turbine subsystem failures from two wind farms in China revealed that 68% of total downtime resulted from issues in the generator and converter systems as well as related to the blades. The proposed solution aims to enable wind farm (WF) operators to proactively monitor operational abnormalities of the generator, allowing for early intervention and improved turbine performance and reliability.

We collected six years of data (2019 - 2024) of an on-shore WF consisting of 10 WTGs, which is located in Greece. During that time period, there were the following major component failures: 7 (64%) generators, 1 (9%) blade, 1 (9%) blade bearing, 1 (9%) bearing/ rotor issue, and 1 (9%) transformer. Hence, the focus of this work is on detecting generator failures. On average, the WTG was offline for almost 38 days in case of a generator failure. Hence, it would be of great value to predict generator failures beforehand so that pre-emptive maintenance can be performed to reduce the downtime.

Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems are used to control and monitor the physical processes at WTGs. SCADA data has proven to be highly promising for detecting anomalies in wind turbine generators. The literature already presents several approaches using different model types, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) and XGBoost, for prediction tasks. However, the performance differences between models are generally small and often depend on the specific wind turbine (e.g., [4]). It has been shown that anomalies can be detected before generator failures occur. However, for real-world applications, it is crucial to

This work has been funded by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG) under grant No. FO999913202 UNDERPIN and by the European Commission under contract No. 101123179 UNDERPIN.

identify such failures ideally as early as possible — up to 60 days - and at least 3 days before the component fails to allow sufficient time for maintenance. Additionally, the false positive rate (e.g., reflected by the precision score) is a key factor for practical use — as a high number of false alarms would reduce the feasibility and acceptance of such systems by wind farm operators.

Hence, our contribution in this paper involves:

- Applying various machine learning models with a focus on the post-processing techniques to optimize detection performance
- Thorough analysis of the performance of predicting the generator’s failure on a large dataset

The remainder of this paper includes the following sections: Section II describes a literature review. Section III describes the methodology, and the experiments are outlined in Section IV. The results are presented in Section V.

II. STATE OF THE ART

Guo et al. [5] developed a generator temperature trend condition monitoring based on a nonlinear state estimate technique model. A failure is detected if an upper confidence interval is exceeded. The work of Cambron et al. [6] monitors an individual wind turbine by comparing the average behavior of the corresponding wind farm. They identify anomalies by a moving average control chart. Udo and Muhammad [4] developed a predictive maintenance system for wind turbines using SCADA data, employing XGBoost and LSTM models for gearbox and generator monitoring. Their main focus was to forecast both temperature values, but they did not analyze detected anomalies in more detail. Garan et al. [7] propose a data-centric instead of a mode-centric approach to predict the remaining useful life of five different components of a WTG. The work of Jankausas et al. [8] deals with the feasibility of early fault detection in wind turbines through RNN-based anomaly detection on gearbox temperature. The post-processing uses two different thresholds based on three standard deviations from the mean value and based on the moving median. Santolamazza et al. [9] predict output power using a Feedforward Neural Network (FNN) and non-linear regression to determine anomalies by detecting residuals above thresholds. The proposed method was tested on an actual wind turbine in Italy. Beretta et al. [10] developed a system addressing wind turbines’ main bearing failure predictions based on SCADA data. Their solution involves combining multiple algorithms, each tailored to detect specific failure patterns, into a unified health status indicator through ensemble learning.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology consists of multiple steps. First, the SCADA data is cleaned and pre-processed so that it is applicable for predictive maintenance of the generator.

A. Pre-processing

The pre-processing of the original data consists of multiple steps:

In the initial pre-processing step, incorrect timestamps in the original data were identified and corrected. Furthermore, periods when the WTG was out of operation due to major component failures were excluded from the training data. Specifically:

- If the generator failed, data from 60 days before the failure and 7 days after the repair were omitted.
- If any other component failed, data from 14 days before the failure and 7 days after repair were excluded.

These exclusions ensure that the training dataset represents only periods when the WTG was operating under normal conditions. Moreover, those data points recorded while the WTG is not in a normal state condition are deleted. For this purpose, we calculate the *Effective Wind Speed Avg.* as the absolute value of the product of *Ambient WindSpeed Avg.* and the cosine of *Ambient WindDir Relative Avg.* The following conditions are used to filter out those data points:

- *Effective Wind Speed Avg.* below 4 m/s. Rows below the cut-in speed of the wind turbine.
- *Effective Wind Speed Avg.* above 25 m/s. Rows exceeding the cut-out speed.
- *Blades PitchAngle Avg.* above 40° are excluded because the power production is manually reduced.
- In addition, outliers in wind turbine power production are eliminated by dynamically adjusting thresholds based on expected power output (see Fig. 1). For this, a smooth power curve is created from the manufacturer’s data to estimate the expected power for each wind speed. Instead of applying a fixed threshold, wind speeds are grouped into 1 m/s bins, and quantile-based thresholds (5th and 95th percentiles) are computed for each bin to account for variations. The thresholds are then applied dynamically, filtering out data points where actual power deviates significantly from the expected range.

B. Feature Selection

The literature review indicates that the generator bearing temperature is frequently used to predict generator health [4]. Consequently, the target variable we aim to model is the generator bearing temperature. We are selecting those sensors in the SCADA data that serve as covariates to predict the current normal operating range of the generator bearing temperature. Larger discrepancies between the predicted and measured generator bearing temperature may indicate a health issue with the generator.

In particular, the target variable is *Generator Bearing Temp. Avg.* and the following covariates are used for prediction:

- *Generator RPM Max.*
- *Nacelle Temp. Avg.*
- *Generator CoolingWater Temp. Avg.*
- *Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 0 Avg.*
- *Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 1 Avg.*

Fig. 1. Wind turbine power curve after filtering process. The manufacturer’s power curve is also displayed.

Fig. 2. Overview of the developed model

- *Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 2 Avg.*

Note that the mean and variance of the generator bearing temperature vary significantly. For instance, the temperature of WTG 1 has 57.9°C (mean) and 293.5°C (variance), while WTG 6 shows 39.2°C (mean) and 109.7°C (variance). Hence, for each WTG, an individual model is trained to predict the generator bearing temperatures.

C. Model Design

The model consists of two parts as depicted in Fig. 2. Firstly, one model predicts the normal operating range of the generator bearing temperature. In a second step, the anomalies are determined by a sliding window mechanism.

As a baseline, we utilize the Quantile Regression Model (QRM) implemented in the scikit-learn library [11]. In addition, we train and evaluate multiple state-of-the-art tree-based ensemble models: CatBoost [12], XGBoost [13], and LightGBM [14]. These models are chosen for their strong generalization performance, ability to model nonlinear relationships, and native support for quantile regression, which is essential for estimating prediction intervals.

Tree-based models offer several advantages for SCADA-based anomaly detection:

- They handle missing data and non-linear feature interactions effectively, which is critical in industrial datasets with complex operating dynamics.
- They are robust to multicollinearity and noise, which often appear in high-frequency sensor data.
- All three frameworks support quantile loss functions, allowing us to directly estimate confidence bounds (e.g., 5th, 50th, and 95th percentiles) rather than relying on post-hoc statistical assumptions.

In our implementation, each model is trained to forecast the generator bearing temperature for a given wind turbine. Rather than using lagged target values, we use covariates derived from current and future SCADA signals (e.g., generator RPM, cooling water temperature, and nacelle temperature), as well as cyclical encodings of the hour and month. This design captures both operational dynamics and seasonal trends. We use a forecast horizon and lag window of 36-time steps (i.e., 6 hours), enabling short-term forecasting that aligns with operational maintenance planning.

To detect anomalies, we evaluate the deviation between predicted and observed temperatures using residual analysis. The first method defines residual thresholds using a moving range control approach [4], [9]. The control limits are computed as follows:

$$\Delta_i = \begin{cases} y_i - \hat{y}_i^{0.05}, & \text{if } |y_i - \hat{y}_i^{0.05}| < |y_i - \hat{y}_i^{0.95}| \\ y_i - \hat{y}_i^{0.95}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$MR_i = |\Delta_i - \Delta_{i-1}|$$

$$\sigma = \frac{\overline{MR}}{1.128}$$

$$UCL = 3\sigma, \quad LCL = -3\sigma$$

where Δ_i is the difference at time point i between the measured temperature y_i and the predicted temperature \hat{y}_i being either the 0.05 or 0.95 quantile prediction - whichever is closer to the measured value. σ is the standard deviation calculated from the ratio of the average moving range \overline{MR} and 1.128. These control limits define a normal operating range. We discard all residuals that are within the thresholds defined by the upper control limit (UCL) and lower control limit (LCL). Hence, only residuals above these thresholds are considered for a potential anomaly. To filter out noise, we apply a sliding window approach that considers a time span of 4 hours. Domain experts deem this duration reasonable for analysis and in alignment with the operators of the WF.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

A. Datasets

The data are generated from an on-shore WF that is located on a Greek island and has been operational since 2009. The island is interconnected with mainland Greece, and the WF consists of 10 WTG. The data used in this study were collected from the SCADA system over six years, from 2019 to 2024. For each WTG, more than 150 values were recorded in the central database every 10 minutes. Data points, where

Fig. 3. Displaying the 8 top features contributing to the model output. Here, the SHAP values of the CatBoost model are presented.

applicable, were collected as minimum, maximum, average, and variance or standard deviation values for each 10-minute interval. For each feature, there were around 3,156,480 values available (aggregated over all 10 WTG).

In the period from 2019 to 2024, there were seven generator failures with information about the date of failure, as well as when the generator was replaced and the WTG was back up and running again. A component failure is considered correctly identified if an anomaly is detected between 3 to 60 days before the failure occurs.

B. Training

We are training all four models using the Darts library [15]. The CatBoost model is configured with 1,200 iterations, a learning rate of 0.03, a depth of 6, L2 leaf regularization set to 3, a random strength of 1, and a border count of 254. The LightGBM model has the following parameter settings: set up with 50 leaves, a learning rate of 0.01, 1,000 estimators, a minimum of 20 data points per leaf, 80% of features used per iteration, 100% of the data used for bagging, and bagging performed every 5 iterations. The XGBoost has the following hyperparameters: number of boosting rounds equals 500, learning rate is set to 0.05, maximum depth is 6 and data sampling set to 0.8.

The impact of the various features on predicting the generator bearing temperature is depicted in Fig. 3. To interpret the SHAP summary plot, the color gradient represents feature values, with colder colors indicating lower values and warmer colors indicating higher values. The x-axis displays SHAP values, which reflect each feature’s influence on fault detection. Negative SHAP values indicate a reduced likelihood of detecting a fault, while positive SHAP values suggest an increased probability of fault occurrence. This visualization helps experts assess model reliability and transparency.

The future lag-1 value of Production LatestAverage Active Power Gen 1 Avg. is the most influential feature, indicating that a higher value at the next time step is associated with an increase in the predicted generator bearing temperature. This is followed by the future lag-1 and lag-2 values of the Generator RPM Max, which exhibit a similar effect. The only feature showing an opposite effect is the encoded month

TABLE I
MODEL ACCURACY FOR PREDICTING GENERATOR BEARING TEMPERATURE BASED ON QUANTILE 0.50 (2019–2020 PERIOD)

WTG	Model	MAPE	RMSE	MAE	UCL
02	QRM	3.69	2.48	1.93	1.12
	CatBoost	2.58	1.73	1.30	1.07
	LightGBM	2.42	1.64	1.22	0.99
	XGBoost	2.44	1.66	1.23	1.14
10	QRM	2.73	1.84	1.48	0.92
	CatBoost	1.19	0.84	0.65	0.90
	LightGBM	1.11	0.81	0.61	0.83
	XGBoost	1.33	1.18	0.76	0.99

cosine, where later months in the year are associated with lower predicted generator bearing temperatures. This likely reflects seasonal trends, as cooler ambient temperatures during these months naturally influence the bearing temperature of the wind turbines.

V. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Data Pre-Processing

As described in Sec. III-A, the pre-processing consists of multiple steps. In a first step, data is excluded that contains either missing data or if the WTG is offline due to some component failures. This reduces the number of data samples from 3,156,480 to 2,927,958. In a second step, those data points are filtered out where the WTG shows an abnormal power production behavior, e.g., due to low wind. By this step, the number of data points is reduced to 1,662,572. The remaining data is depicted in Fig. 1.

B. Anomaly Detection

Firstly, the models’ capabilities to predict the temperature is analyzed. For this, different error metrics are calculated as shown in Tab. I. The accuracy of the forecasts is improved significantly by moving from QRM to tree-based models. On the other hand, the differences in accuracy among the three tree-based models are small, and their ranking varies depending on the WTG. Since the QRM model performs significantly worse at predicting generator temperature compared to the tree-based models, it does not seem suitable for anomaly detection and is therefore excluded from further analysis.

In Tab. II, different error metrics of the anomaly detection are presented. For this, the precision, recall, and accuracy are calculated for all tree-based models. The highest recall score is achieved by the CatBoost model, which is able to detect all failures. The LightGBM and XGBoost models detect 6 and 5 failures, respectively. The precision of all models is low ($\approx 4.8e-3$) due to the large number of false positives. The accuracy of all models is above 99.6%.

Fig. 4 presents an example with the measured *Generator Bearing Temperature Average* shown as a black line, while the predicted values based on the 50th percentile are shown in green. The normal operating range is illustrated by the shaded mint-green area, defined by the 5th and 95th percentiles, representing the lower and upper bounds, respectively. The

TABLE II
RESULTS OF THE ANOMALY DETECTION (2019–2024 PERIOD).

Model	TP	FN	FP	Precision	Recall	Accuracy
CatBoost	7	0	1461	4.8e-3	1.0	99.6%
LightGBM	6	1	1263	4.7e-3	0.86	99.7%
XGBoost	5	2	1465	4.1e-3	0.71	99.6%

detected anomalies are presented in lilac, and the true failure occurs on November 25, 2019 (displayed in pink).

C. Discussion

The most critical task is to identify a component failure in advance. This kind of anomaly detection is very challenging because of the few component failures in the dataset, resulting in highly imbalanced classes. The trained models show good results in detecting those failures, as shown by the high recall scores. For practical application, however, a low false positive rate is equally important. Our results indicate that a high number of false alarms still occur, leading to a low precision score, which makes real-world implementation challenging. Hence, it is critical to continue working on this approach by either improving the presented models and post-processing steps or including additional SCADA sensors, which also relate to the health status of the generator. For instance, features like *Generator Stator Temperature*, *Generator Voltage Avg.*, and *Generator Current Avg.* could support to determine the health status of the generator and decrease the number of false positives. Unfortunately, these features are currently not available in the recorded dataset.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a proactive fault detection solution was developed, which consists of the following steps: 1) data pre-processing, 2) predicting the generator bearing temperature, and 3) anomaly detection. The data pre-processing ensured that only data points were kept where the WTG was in a normal condition with respect to the effective wind speed and expected power production. The cleaned data was used to train a QRM as well as tree-based models to predict the generator bearing temperature. The difference between the predicted versus measured generator bearing temperature was the basis for identifying anomalies, which indicate a potential component failure. In particular, the CatBoost model achieved very good results in detecting these failures and help contributing to more reliable and cost-effective wind farm operations. In future work, we aim to refine the developed models as well as to add additional features to improve precision while keeping a high recall rate.

REFERENCES

[1] S. Liu, S. Ren, and H. Jiang, "Predictive maintenance of wind turbines based on digital twin technology," *Energy Reports*, vol. 9, pp. 1344–1352, 2023.
[2] M. I. Blanco, "The economics of wind energy," *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews*, vol. 13, no. 6-7, pp. 1372–1382, 2009.

[3] Y. Zhao, D. Li, A. Dong, D. Kang, Q. Lv, and L. Shang, "Fault prediction and diagnosis of wind turbine generators using scada data," *Energies*, vol. 10, no. 8, p. 1210, 2017.
[4] W. Udo and Y. Muhammad, "Data-driven predictive maintenance of wind turbine based on scada data," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 162 370–162 388, 2021.
[5] P. Guo, D. Infield, and X. Yang, "Wind turbine generator condition-monitoring using temperature trend analysis," *IEEE Transactions on sustainable energy*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 124–133, 2011.
[6] P. Cambron, C. Masson, A. Tahan, and F. Pelletier, "Control chart monitoring of wind turbine generators using the statistical inertia of a wind farm average," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 116, pp. 88–98, 2018.
[7] M. Garan, K. Tidri, and I. Kovalenko, "A data-centric machine learning methodology: Application on predictive maintenance of wind turbines," *Energies*, vol. 15, no. 3, p. 826, 2022.
[8] M. Jankauskas, A. Serackis, M. Šapurov, R. Pomarnacki, A. Baskys, V. K. Hyunh, T. Vaimann, and J. Zakis, "Exploring the limits of early predictive maintenance in wind turbines applying an anomaly detection technique," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 12, p. 5695, 2023.
[9] A. Santolamazza, D. Dadi, and V. Introna, "A data-mining approach for wind turbine fault detection based on scada data analysis using artificial neural networks," *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 7, p. 1845, 2021.
[10] M. Beretta, A. Julian, J. Sepulveda, J. Cusidó, and O. Porro, "An ensemble learning solution for predictive maintenance of wind turbines main bearing," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 4, p. 1512, 2021.
[11] F. Pedregosa, G. Varoquaux, A. Gramfort, V. Michel, B. Thirion, O. Grisel, M. Blondel, P. Prettenhofer, R. Weiss, V. Dubourg *et al.*, "Scikit-learn: Machine learning in python," *the Journal of machine Learning research*, vol. 12, pp. 2825–2830, 2011.
[12] L. Prokhorenkova, G. Gusev, A. Vorobev, A. V. Dorogush, and A. Gulin, "Catboost: unbiased boosting with categorical features," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 31, 2018.
[13] T. Chen and C. Guestrin, "Xgboost: A scalable tree boosting system," in *Proceedings of the 22nd acm sigkdd international conference on knowledge discovery and data mining*, 2016, pp. 785–794.
[14] G. Ke, Q. Meng, T. Finley, T. Wang, W. Chen, W. Ma, Q. Ye, and T.-Y. Liu, "Lightgbm: A highly efficient gradient boosting decision tree," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 30, 2017.
[15] J. Herzen, F. Lässig, S. G. Piazzetta, T. Neuer, L. Tafti, G. Raille, T. Van Pottelbergh, M. Pasięka, A. Skrodzki, N. Huguenin *et al.*, "Darts: User-friendly modern machine learning for time series," *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 23, no. 124, pp. 1–6, 2022.

Fig. 4. Results of monitoring WTG 5, including predicted anomalies (highlighted in lilac) and the true failure event (highlighted in pink).